

Source: Nemati, A., Shadpour, S., Khalafbeygi, H., Ashraf, S., Barkhi, M., & [Soudi, M. R.](#) (2015). Efficiency of Hydrothermal Synthesis of Nano/Microsized Copper and Study on In Vitro Antifungal Activity. *Materials and Manufacturing Processes*, 30(1), 63-69, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10426914.2014.941873>

Efficiency of hydrothermal synthesis of Nano/micro sized copper and study on In vitro antifungal activity

Ahlam Nemati^{1,4}, Sasan Shadpour^{1,4}, Hamid Khalafbeygi¹, Simin Ashraf², Mohammad Barkhi^{3,4}, [Mohammad Reza Soudi](#)²

¹Department of Chemistry, Islamic Azad University, Karaj branch, Karaj, Iran,

²Department of Biology, Al-zahra University, Tehran, Iran,

³Department of Chemistry, Applied-Scientific University, Zar Branch, Karaj, Iran,

⁴Nano system Research Team (NRTeam, NGO), Karaj, Iran

Corresponding Author to Ahlam Nemati: Department of Chemistry, Islamic Azad

Abstract

In this study, the synthesis and characterization of copper nano/micro particles in the presence of (2,2',2'',2'''-(ethane-1,2-diylbis(azanetriyl))tetraacetohydrazide) as a capping and reducing agent under hydrothermal conditions for use in biological conditions were investigated. The effects of reductant -ligand/copper-ion, concentration ratios, reaction temperatures, and reaction time on the various morphologies of copper nano/micro particles were studied. The obtained particles have been characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive X-ray spectrum analysis (EDS), and zeta potential analysis. Further, the formation of particles with different morphologies was confirmed. The biological and antifungal effects of these particles selected particles were compared with those of Bordeaux mixture. Experiments were conducted on *Alternaria alternata*, *Alternaria solani* and *Fusarium expansum*, as three types of phytopathogenic fungi and penicillium as a non-phytopathogenic fungus. The results obtained showed that not only were the nano/microparticles more effective than Bordeaux mixture in killing phytopathogenic fungi, but also these particles did not have a fungicidal effect on the non-phytopathogenic fungus, penicillium, which is an advantage of the obtained nano/microparticles.

KEYWORDS: Nanoparticles, Morphology, Hydrothermal, Antifungal, Electron, Microscopy.